

Systematic Review of Human Resource Management Demand in the Fourth Industrial Revolution Era: Implication of Upskilling, Reskilling and Deskilling

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Abstract

Human resources are essential to an organization's performance, competitiveness, and sustainability in any industrial revolution era. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) integrates advanced technologies and the convergence of physical, digital, and biological systems, offering HR professionals opportunities and threats. This study examines the implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) on upskilling, reskilling, and deskilling of Human resource management. The study adopted a systematic review of relevant literature on the various issues addressed in the research. The study critically analyzed 38 relevant research journals, articles, publications, opinions, and editorials on human resource management demand in the fourth industrial revolution era. The study revealed that 4IR technologies, such as AI and robotics, could accomplish jobs more effectively than humans, leading to deskilling. Adopting 4IR technologies will also require HR personnel to upskill in digital literacy, data analysis, programming, cyber-security, HR software analytics, emotional intelligence, and critical thinking. The study also revealed that HR personnel would need to reskill to acquire proficiency using 4IR technologies. The study concludes that adopting 4IR technologies will result in upskilling, reskilling, and deskilling of human resources. The study recommends that organizations invest in training and development programs to upskill and reskill HR personnel, regular skills assessments to identify obsolete skills, implementing training programs that meet the changing needs of the job, and developing a comprehensive workforce development strategy to consider alternative approaches to job design that prioritize the development of new skills and knowledge.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), Upskilling, Reskilling, Deskilling

Introduction

Human resources management (HRM) remains an appropriate strategic approach to managing people in organizations across the globe. This function is indispensable in managing an organization's

workforce toward achieving its stated objectives and sustainability in a dynamic competitive business environment. HRM function comprised recruitment, selection, training and development, performance management, compensation, and benefits, employee relations, and employment laws and regulations compliance. The primary goal of HRM is to attract, retain and develop a skilled and motivated workforce that can contribute to the organization's success. HRM is critical in aligning the organization's human resources with its business strategy and goals. By managing the people in the organization effectively, HRM can help improve employee morale, productivity, and job satisfaction, leading to increased profitability and organizational success ((Garengo, Sardi, & Nudurupati, 2022)).

The fourth industrial revolution, also known as 4IR or Industry 4.0, has permeated the human economy and every area of human life due to its efficiency, and dynamic nature. 4IR, which is characterized by the intersection of the digital, biological, and physical worlds and the increasing use of new technologies like artificial intelligence, cloud computing, robotics, 3D printing, the Internet of Things, and advanced wireless technologies, among others, has brought about a new era of economic implications. These technologies are required to optimize resources, a prerequisite for achieving economic, environmental, and social sustainability. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) created a new wave of innovation and transformation in various fields. It built upon the previous three industrial revolutions that brought mechanization, mass production, and automation to industry.

The 4IR presents numerous opportunities for HR professionals and organizations in the automation of repetitive tasks. With the help of technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), HR professionals can automate many repetitive tasks, such as resume screening, interview scheduling, and onboarding. The advent of 4IR also improved talent management and employee engagement, increased personalized learning and development, enhanced recruitment and retention, and improved HR analytics (Oosthuizen, 2022a; Votto, Valecha, Najafirad, & Rao, 2021). While the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) presents numerous opportunities for human resources (HR) professionals and organizations, it poses several threats. With the advent of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics, there is a risk that many jobs could be automated, resulting in job losses and a shift in the types of skills and jobs in demand, leading to deskilling (Oosthuizen, 2022b). The rapid pace of technological change also means risk, as many workers may not have the skills to keep up with new technologies and trends. This could result in widening skills and income gaps and a shortage of workers with the skills needed to fill new roles resulting in reskilling and upskilling (Zervoudi, 2020).

Chashi & Mwanza (2022) asserted in the study of the influence of the fourth industrial revolution on human resources within the Zambian banking sector, revealed that 4IR had alleviated tedious, repetitive tasks and paved the way for upskilling opportunities. In contrast, identified threats include difficulty learning a new skill, the fear of losing one's job, and reliance on technology that slows work during machine downtime. Ahn, Jang & Rhee (2022), in the study of a factor exploration and

empirical study on the influence of the fourth industrial revolution on employment, revealed that 4IR technologies such as self-driving cars, decision-making using big data, wearable internet, the Internet of Things, blockchain and 3D printing technology had significant positive effects on the employment function of HRM. Adegbite & Adeosun (2021), in a study of Fourth Industrial Revolution Skillsets and Employability Readiness for Future Job, also revealed that 4IR presents opportunities for upskilling and deskilling as the majority of employable skill sets in the 4IR are viewed as low among the sampled organization employees.

Several studies have been undertaken on the advent of the fourth industrial revolution and the role of human resources in the 4IR era. However, limited research has been carried out on the implications of 4IR on Human resource management personnel saddled with the responsibility of managing an organization's human resources. Consequently, this spurs the need to explore the implication of 4IR on human resource management personnel. This study examines the implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) on Human resource management personnel. Specific objectives include:

1. Assess the implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on deskilling of Human Resources Management.
2. Examine the implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on upskilling of Human Resources Management.
3. Examine the implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on reskilling of Human Resources Management.

Literature Review

Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR)

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) is a term used to describe the current era of technological innovation, characterized by the fusion of technologies that blur the lines between the physical, digital, and biological worlds (David, Nwulu, Aigbavboa, & Adepoju, 2022). The fourth industrial revolution, or 4IR, was first described by Klaus Schwab, regarded as the father of the 4IR, as an extension of the third industrial revolution and a distinct revolution that the world has never seen (Singaram & Mayer, 2022). The development of the steam engine in 1760 marked the beginning of the first industrial revolution. The steam engine made it possible to move from farming and a feudal civilization to a modern manufacturing system (Xu, David & Kim, 2018). In this phase, railways served as the primary mode of transportation, and coal was the primary energy source.

The internal combustion engine's development in 1900 marked the start of the second industrial revolution. This sparked a period of rapid industrialization that relied on electricity and oil to drive mass production (Mohajan, 2020). The third industrial revolution began in 1960 and was marked by adoption

of electronics and information technologies to automate production. The traditional manufacturing methods entailed joining numerous parts using screws or welding (Oztemel & Gursev, 2020). The fourth industrial revolution includes computer-generated product design and three-dimensional (3D) printing, which can produce solid objects by stacking up successive layers of materials (Dogaru, 2020; Kantaros et al., 2022).

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is characterized by technological advancements' speed and scale, impacting traditional business models, processes, and social structures (Dogaru, 2020; Moll, 2021). Some critical features of 4IR include the rise of smart factories, autonomous vehicles, personalized medicine, and big data analytics to make data-driven decisions (Fanoro, Božani'cbožani, & Sinha, 2021). The Fourth Industrial Revolution has the potential to create significant benefits, such as increased efficiency, productivity, and innovation (Ross & Maynard, 2021), but it also presents new challenges and risks, including job displacement, privacy concerns, and security threats (Abdelmajied, 2022; Ajayi, Bagula & Maluleke, 2022). As such, policymakers, businesses, and individuals must understand and navigate the impacts and opportunities of 4IR to ensure a sustainable and equitable future.

Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) Technologies

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) refers to the ongoing transformation of the traditional manufacturing and industrial sector through the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, the Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, and virtual and augmented reality (Fanoro et al., 2021; Raja Santhi & Muthuswamy, 2023). Alsulaimani & Islam (2022) stated that these technologies are used to create smart factories, intelligent supply chains, and innovative products and services that are changing how we live and work. Anderson & Rainie(2018) and Xu et al. (2021) asserted that artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are the potential of computers and technological applications to accomplish complex human-like tasks with more intelligence and capacity. It is a technical application having human-like features that enable machines to learn from data, recognizes patterns, and make decisions (Hee Lee & Yoon, 2021; Xu et al., 2021), while robotics and automation is an interdisciplinary field that combines electro-mechatronics, computer science, and information engineering to generate and manage sensory input and information for supporting tasks and activities that take the place of human operations (Kondo, 2012; Macario-Rojas, Parslew, Weightman, & Smith., 2022). Robotic technology assists and replaces humans in production activities because of their high intelligence and practical completion of specified duties. It is also used in manufacturing, healthcare, and other sectors to perform repetitive or dangerous tasks (Coombs, Hislop, Taneva & Barnard, 2020; Javaid, Haleem, Singh, & Suman, 2021).

The fourth industrial revolution also centres on the Internet of Things (IoT), a network of physical items with integrated technology to interact, communicate and perceive their internal states

and external environment. The internet connects at least 25.6 billion objects, improving the quality of life and productivity of society, people, and businesses/industries. IoT underpins smart life, cities, energy, transport, industry, health, buildings, and housing (Adebayo, Numbu, & Chaubey, 2019; Javaid et al., 2022). Furthermore, Virtual reality is a computer-generated simulation or artificial replication of a real-life environment or situation that aims to immerse the user by giving him the idea that he is experiencing the simulated reality, primarily through stimulation of his vision and ears. By superimposing computer-generated virtual content on actual structures, augmented reality (AR) is a type of technology that enhances the sensory perception of reality. These technologies create immersive experiences for users, allowing them to interact with digital environments in new ways (Cipresso, Giglioli, Raya & Riva, 2018; Xiong, Hsiang, He, Zhan, & Wu, 2021).

Human Resource Management Practices in the Fourth Industrial Revolution Era

Human Resource Planning

A significant expectation of HRM is ensuring the availability of an adequate number of personnel with the required skills. This function is known as Human resource planning. This is a process of forecasting an organization's future staffing needs and developing strategies and plans to meet those needs. It involves identifying the organization's current and future workforce requirements, analyzing labour supply and demand, and developing strategies to recruit, train, and retain employees (Samwel, 2018; Sujay & Khadilkar, 2019). George (2019) affirmed that human resource planning aims to ensure that the organization has the right people with the right skills in the right jobs and at the right time. This helps organizations to effectively achieve their goals and objectives, improve productivity and performance, and reduce the cost of employee turnover.

Before the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), human resources planning (HRP) primarily involved traditional methods and tools, which were mainly paper-based and relied on manual processes (Dhanpat, Buthelezi, Joe, Maphela, & Shongwe 2020; Narasimhan, 2021a). Standard HRP practices used paper files, forms and registers, and postal mail. These traditional HR tools were inefficient and time-consuming, and they required a significant amount of manual effort. However, with 4IR technologies such as automation, AI, and machine learning, HRP has become more advanced and automated, streamlining processes and improving efficiency (Rafique, Asim, & Manzoor 2021; Sima, Gheorghe, Subić, & Nancu, 2020).

Artificial intelligence (AI) and automation have revolutionized human resource (HR) planning. Through predictive analytics, AI algorithms analyze large volumes of data to predict future workforce needs based on past trends, turnover rates, and business projections (Broby, 2022). Machine learning algorithms can also analyze historical data on employee turnover rates, retirement rates, and other factors to predict future workforce needs (Fallucchi et al., 2020). Pourkhodabakhsh, Mamoudan, &

Bozorgi-Amiri (2022) asserted that this could help HR departments plan for future staffing needs and identify areas where skills gaps may exist. AI can also help optimize workforce scheduling to ensure the right people are in the right place at the right time. This allows organizations to maximize their efficiency and reduce costs associated with overstaffing or understaffing.

Additionally, Machine learning algorithms can analyze employee feedback data from surveys, social media, and other sources to identify trends in employee sentiment (Pourkhodabakhsh et al., 2022). This can help HR managers identify areas to improve employee satisfaction and engagement (Yang & Islam, 2020). 4IR technologies such as automation and artificial intelligence (AI) can help streamline HR processes and reduce manual labour, freeing HR professionals to focus on more strategic tasks leading to increased efficiency. Data analytics tools can also provide HR professionals with real-time insights to make more informed and data-driven decisions (Luo et al., 2023; Majam & Jarbandhan, 2022).

Recruitment and Selection

Acquiring the right employee for an organization lies in the strategic function of HRM, which is called the recruitment and selection process. Recruitment refers to identifying and attracting potential candidates for a job opening. This process typically involves advertising job vacancies on various platforms such as job boards, social media, and company websites and sourcing candidates through employee referrals and recruitment agencies (Kapur, 2018). Recruitment aims to generate a pool of qualified candidates who can be screened and selected for further consideration. Conversely, selection refers to evaluating and choosing the most suitable candidate from the collection of applicants generated during the recruitment process (Daniel, Abba-Sanda, & Salau-Midala, 2014). The selection process typically involves the initial screening of resumes and applications, interviews, skills assessment tests, background checks, and reference checks. The objective of the selection process is to choose the candidate with the necessary skills, qualifications, experience, and personality traits required for the job and who will fit well with the company's culture and values (Ekwoaba, Ikeije, & Ufoma, 2015).

Before the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), recruitment and selection were mainly conducted through traditional newspaper ads, journals, magazines, word-of-mouth referrals, and recruitment agencies. Job advertisements are contained in these publications, and interested candidates respond by submitting their resumes and cover letters by post or in person (Narasimhan, 2021b). Companies also relied on referrals from current employees, clients, and business associates. Recruitment agencies were also used, where companies would outsource finding candidates to specialized recruitment firms. These firms would typically pre-screen candidates, interview them, and present them to the company for final selection. The selection was usually made through in-person interviews, and candidates would be assessed based on their qualifications, experience, and personality

fit with the company culture. Tests such as aptitude tests, personality tests, and assessments were also conducted to assess a candidate's suitability for the role (Al-Kassem, 2017; Bhaker, 2020).

The 4IR has revolutionized the recruitment and selection process due to introducing emerging technologies. These technologies use artificial intelligence (AI) and automation to streamline and enhance recruitment and selection processes. AI-based software can screen and analyze resumes and identify the most qualified candidates based on their skills, education, and experience (Narasimhan, 2021b; Nidhi Oswal, Khaleeli, & Alarmoti 2020). This technology saves time and resources by eliminating the need for manual screening of resumes. Chatbots and virtual assistants can provide candidates with information about job openings, application status, and other relevant information. These technologies can also answer frequently asked questions, freeing HR professionals to focus on more complex tasks (Caldarini, Jaf, & McGarry 2022; Nawaz & Gomes, 2020).

Additionally, AI-powered video interviewing software allows recruiters to conduct interviews remotely, saving time and resources while still allowing them to evaluate candidates effectively. This software can identify traits like confidence and communication skills and analyze facial expressions, tone of voice, and other non-verbal cues to determine the best candidates (Joshi, Bloom, Spencer, Gaetke-Udager, & Cohan 2020). Employers can connect with potential candidates from anywhere via video conferencing and other digital tools. VR and AR technologies are also used in recruitment to give candidates a more immersive experience of the company culture and work environment. VR and AR can also simulate job-related scenarios and test candidates' problem-solving skills (Zhang & Wang, 2021). Predictive analytics can forecast hiring needs, optimize recruitment strategies, and identify potential attrition risks. 4IR technologies offer significant benefits for recruitment and selection, improving efficiency, objectivity, candidate experience, quality of hires, and cost savings (Ejo-Orusa & Okwakpam, 2018; Kashive & Khanna, 2022).

Performance Appraisal

Organizational success relies on employee performance, which demands human resource management designing appraisal methods to achieve these objectives. The performance appraisal process involves setting performance expectations, providing employee feedback, assessing their progress, and making decisions about employee development, compensation, and promotions (van Dijk & Schodl, 2015). Performance appraisals are conducted annually, semi-annually, or more frequently (Iqbal , Akbar, Budhwar, & Shah., 2019; van Woerkom & Kroon, 2020).

Before the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), performance appraisals were typically done through a formal process where managers or supervisors would evaluate an employee's performance based on predefined criteria (Kromrei, 2015). The process was usually conducted through a face-to-face meeting between the employee and their manager or supervisor. During the meeting, the employee's performance would be assessed based on various criteria, such as productivity, quality of work,

communication skills, teamwork, and adherence to company policies and procedures (Rotatori, Lee & Sleeva 2021). A lack of transparency and objectivity in the appraisal process and potential biases from the manager or supervisor characterized the traditional performance appraisal method. Additionally, performance appraisals were often conducted annually, which could delay addressing performance issues or providing timely employee feedback (Al-Baidhani & Alsaqqaf, 2022).

Employee performance appraisal using Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) technologies in human resources management is a relatively new concept gaining popularity due to its ability to provide more objective and accurate employee performance assessments (Budhwar, Malik, De-Silva & Thevisuthan, 2022). HR professionals can use AI-powered assessment tools such as machine learning algorithms, chatbots, and natural language processing to automate evaluating employee performance. These tools can analyze employee data such as productivity, attendance, and communication patterns to objectively and accurately assess employee performance (Gunathunge & Lakmal, 2021). Wearable technology such as smartwatches and fitness trackers can be used to monitor an employee's performance in real time, providing feedback on their physical activity, stress levels, and other metrics that can impact their job performance. This can help identify areas where the employee may need support, such as stress management or physical wellness (Oosthuizen, 2022b).

Additionally, gamification involves using game mechanics such as points, badges, and leaderboards to motivate employees and encourage them to perform better. This approach can be used in performance appraisal to create a more engaging and interactive process that encourages employees to strive for excellence (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017a; Howard & Bevins, 2018). HR professionals can also use data analytics tools to analyze large amounts of employee data and identify patterns and trends that can help identify areas of strengths and weaknesses. This data can be used to provide more objective and accurate assessments of employee performance. Using 4IR technologies in performance appraisal can give real-time feedback, more objective evaluations and increased accuracy. 4IR technologies help HR professionals achieve increased efficiency, improved employee engagement, and better alignment with organizational goals (Abdelmajied, 2022; Fanoro et al., 2021).

Learning and Development

The highly dynamic, ever-changing, and competitive business environment relies greatly on human resource management to constantly develop training and developmental programs. It involves providing employees with training, coaching, mentoring, and other learning opportunities to develop their competencies and prepare them for new organizational roles or responsibilities (Alharthy & Marni, 2020). The primary goal of learning and development is to support the organization's strategic objectives by ensuring that employees have the necessary KSAs to perform their jobs effectively and efficiently. It also helps to improve employee engagement, retention, and job satisfaction and enhances the organization's overall performance and competitiveness (Salas, Tannenbaum, Kraiger & Smith-

Jentsch, 2012). Before the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), learning and development in human resources management were primarily done through traditional methods such as classroom-style training, on-the-job training, coaching, and mentoring (Reaves, 2019).

Classroom-style training was a standard method where employees would attend training sessions in a physical classroom environment. The training would be delivered by a trainer or instructor covering a specific topic or skill set related to the employees' job roles. This method was helpful in simultaneously developing a large group of employees (Darling-Hammond, Flook, Cook-Harvey, Barron & Osher, 2019). On-the-job training was another traditional method where employees would learn and develop new skills by observing and working alongside experienced colleagues. This method was effective for jobs that required hands-on experience and specific technical skills, such as manufacturing or construction (Basariya. s. Rabiyaatul & Sree, 2019). Coaching and mentoring were also commonly used traditional methods for learning and development. Employees would work with a coach or mentor who would provide guidance and feedback on their performance and help them develop new skills and knowledge related to their job roles (Al Hilali, Mughairi, Kian & Karim 2020; Gamage, Perera & Wijewardena, 2021). Traditional learning and development methods were effective in their time, but they had limitations regarding scalability, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019; Hennessy et al., 2022).

With the emergence of digital technologies and the Fourth Industrial Revolution, new and innovative approaches to learning and development have become available, such as e-learning, gamification, virtual reality, and artificial intelligence. These technologies are being used to create innovative learning solutions that are more efficient, effective, and engaging than traditional methods (Arek-Bawa & Reddy, 2022; Lase, 2019). Virtual and augmented reality technologies have created immersive learning experiences that simulate real-world scenarios. This allows employees to practice skills and techniques in a safe, controlled environment without risk to themselves or others (Kuhail et al., 2022; Meccawy, 2022). AI-powered learning solutions are also used to personalize employee learning experiences based on their learning styles, preferences, and performance. AI can also analyze data to identify skill gaps and recommend learning paths tailored to each employee's needs (Chaudhry & Kazim, 2021). Gamification is being used to make learning more engaging and fun. Adding game elements like points, badges, and leaderboards to learning activities motivates employees to participate and compete with each other, leading to increased learning retention and engagement (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017b; Saleem, Noori & Ozdamli, 2022).

With the rise of mobile technology, organizations use mobile learning solutions to deliver training and development content to employees anytime, anywhere. This allows employees to learn at their own pace and schedule, increasing engagement and retention (Alajmi, Khambari, Luan & Rahim 2020). Additionally, 4IR technologies enable personalized learning that caters to the employee's unique learning style and pace. This ensures that the employee grasps the concepts better and retains the

knowledge for longer. With 4IR technologies, employees can collaborate with their peers, mentors, and experts from across the globe, breaking down geographical barriers. 4IR technologies also enable the creation of reusable digital content, reducing the cost of creating and distributing learning materials. They also provide real-time feedback to employees, helping them to identify their strengths and weaknesses and tailor their learning accordingly. 4IR technologies enable employees to continuously learn through microlearning, gamification, and mobile learning, ensuring that they stay up-to-date with the latest developments in their field (Hameed & Hashim, 2022; Oke & Fernandes, 2020).

Employee Relations

Employee Relations in human resources management refers to how an organization manages the relationships between its employees and the organization itself. It involves creating and maintaining a positive and productive work environment, fostering communication and collaboration between employees and management, and ensuring that the rights and well-being of employees are respected and protected (Oke & Fernandes, 2020). Effective employee relations involve addressing and resolving workplace issues such as conflicts, grievances, and disciplinary actions fairly and equitably. It also encompasses providing employees with opportunities for training and development, feedback and recognition, and work-life balance, all of which contribute to a positive employee experience and increased job satisfaction (Taslim Ahammad, 2017).

Before the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), traditional human resource management methods were used to manage employee relations. These conventional methods were paper-based and manual, relying heavily on face-to-face communication and interpersonal skills. They were also often time-consuming and labour-intensive and required significant administrative and record-keeping efforts (Bayraktar & Atac, 2018; Mayer, Wegerle & Oosthuizen, 2021). Organizations created employee handbooks and policies to provide guidelines and expectations for employee behaviour, work schedules, benefits, and other related matters. These documents were often distributed to employees through print copies or in-person orientations. Management and union leaders negotiated collective bargaining agreements in unionized workplaces to establish working conditions, wages, and employee benefits. These agreements were typically negotiated through face-to-face meetings between management and union representatives. Organizations had formal grievance procedures to address employee complaints and disputes. These procedures involved written documentation, investigation, and resolution by management and human resources staff (Obiekwe & Eke, 2019).

In the 4th Industrial Revolution (4IR), modern technologies transformed how employee relations are managed in human resources management. Many organizations now use digital employee handbooks and Employee Self-Service (ESS) Platforms where employees can manage their HR-related tasks, such as requesting time off, updating personal information, and accessing training and development resources, that are accessible through the company's intranet or a mobile app without

having to go through a human resources representative (Quaosar & Rahman, 2021). Employee engagement platforms use data analytics and AI to track employee sentiment and engagement. This data is used to identify improvement areas, design targeted engagement strategies, and allow employees to access the information they need and receive real-time updates effortlessly (Halid, Yusoff & Somu, 2020). AI-powered Chatbots are also used to answer frequently asked questions and provide immediate assistance to employees. They have been integrated into messaging platforms and the company's website to provide 24/7 support to employees (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021; Ruan & Mezei, 2022). Cloud-based HR management systems also allow centralized employee data management, providing HR staff easy access to employee records, payroll, benefits, and attendance (Silva & Lima, 2017). Social media and collaboration tools such as Slack, Microsoft Teams, and Zoom are also used to facilitate communication and collaboration between employees and management. These tools enable remote work and offer new opportunities for global partnership (Wong, Ho, Olusanya, Antonini & Lyness, 2020).

Upskilling, Reskilling and Deskilling

Upskilling is a skill development concept that has become required in the advent /era of the introduction of technology. New roles are introduced to employees from time to time, requiring upskilling. It refers to enhancing an employee's existing skills and knowledge to improve their performance in their current job or prepare them for future job opportunities. It can involve acquiring new technical skills, developing soft skills, or gaining knowledge of new processes or tools (Chaaya, Abou Hamad & Beyrouthy 2019). Causes of upskilling can include technological advancements, changes like work, and the need to remain competitive in the job market. For example, as automation and artificial intelligence become more prevalent, workers must develop new skills to stay relevant (Chaaya et al., 2019). The consequences of upskilling can be both positive and negative. On the positive side, upskilling can increase productivity, job satisfaction, and wages. It can also lead to a more diverse and resilient workforce. On the negative side, upskilling can be costly and time-consuming, and not all workers may have equal access to upskilling opportunities, which can exacerbate existing inequalities in the workforce. Additionally, some workers may feel overwhelmed or stressed by the pressure to constantly learn and adapt to new skills and technologies (Chakrabarti, 2022; Jaiswal, Arun & Varma, 2021; Li, 2022).

On the other hand, reskilling is acquiring new skills or upgrading existing ones to perform a new job or adapt to changes in technology or business processes. In human resources management, reskilling is strategy organizations use to develop and retain employees by helping them acquire the necessary skills and competencies to meet the changing demands of their jobs or the labour market (Penesis et al., 2017; Sawant, Thomas & Kadlag 2022). Reskilling involves developing an employee's skills in a new area to perform a different job or adapt to changes in the labour market. The causes of

reskilling are numerous and include changes in technology, changes in the organization's strategic goals or priorities, the emergence of new job roles or industries, and the need to adapt to new regulations or industry standards. For example, automating specific job functions may require employees to acquire new technical skills to work alongside machines.

In contrast, changes in business models may require employees to learn new soft skills, such as collaboration and agility (Gowrie Vinayan et al., 2020). The consequences of reskilling are generally positive for both employees and organizations. Employees who acquire new skills may experience increased job satisfaction, career advancement opportunities, and higher salaries. Organizations that invest in reskilling their workforce can benefit from increased productivity, improved employee engagement and retention, and a more agile and adaptable workforce that can quickly respond to changes in the market or the competitive landscape (Jaiswal et al., 2021; Yaseen et al., 2022).

Deskilling reduces the knowledge, skills, and abilities required for a particular job or task. In human resources management, deskilling can occur when an organization replaces skilled workers with less skilled workers or when technology replaces workers altogether (Kunst, 2020). Causes of deskilling can include automation, outsourcing, offshoring, and cost-cutting measures. Automation, for example, can replace skilled workers with machines that require less training and can perform tasks faster and more consistently. Outsourcing and offshoring can lead to losing professional jobs in a particular region or country as organizations seek to take advantage of lower labour costs elsewhere. Cost-cutting measures can also lead to deskilling, as organizations reduce the training and support they provide workers (Previtali & Fagiani, 2015; Sambasivan & Veeraraghavan, 2022). On the positive side, deskilling can reduce organizational labour costs, increase efficiency, and improve product quality. However, the negative consequences of deskilling are more profound. Deskilling can lead to increased job insecurity, reduced job satisfaction, and lower worker wages (Jang et al., 2021; Martinaitis et al., 2020). Deskilling can also contribute to a decline in overall skill levels in the workforce, negatively affecting innovation and productivity. Overall, deskilling is a significant concern for human resources management, as it can have important implications for workers, organizations, and society as a whole.

Methodology

This study utilized a systematic literature review methodology through collecting and analyzing empirical literature and non-numerical data to contextualize opinions, understand an experience, and juxtapose concepts, which helps a researcher gather in-depth insights into a problem to generate new ideas (Tawfik et al., 2019). The systematic literature review is a methodical and comprehensive approach to identifying, evaluating, and synthesizing all available research evidence on the research topic (Snyder, 2019). The strength of the systematic review lies in its rigorous methodology, which minimizes the risk of bias and ensures that all relevant evidence is considered. The authors searched peer-reviewed journal articles on HRM demand in the Fourth Industrial Revolution era, upskilling,

reskilling, and deskilling implications, and human resource studies conducted between 2015 and 2023. This period of time enables an analysis of HRM demand during the 4IR's early phases and offers insight into the evolving landscape up until the present time. We searched PubMed, PsycINFO, Business Source Complete, Web of Science, Scopus, IEEE Xplore and Google Scholar databases. We searched for peer-reviewed articles and conference proceedings containing the following keywords in the title or abstract: "human resource management" (HRM demand OR HR demand) AND ("Fourth Industrial Revolution" OR "Industry 4.0") AND (upskilling OR reskilling OR deskilling). Articles from well-established HRM, organizational behaviour, or management journals, such as the Journal of Applied Psychology, Human Resource Management, Personnel Psychology, and Journal of Organizational Behavior, were selected. Conference proceedings from the Chartered Institute of Personnel Management of Nigeria (CIPM) were also explored. An initial broad search to capture a wide range of articles on human resources management and the fourth industrial revolution produced 154 pieces. Thus, we excluded all duplicate articles and non-peer-reviewed publications, articles that do not directly address HRM demand or the implications of upskilling, reskilling, and deskilling and studies conducted in industries or sectors unrelated to human resources. Additionally, the following keywords were used to select the articles which will be included in this study: Human resource management, Fourth Industrial Revolution, Industry 4.0, Digital transformation, Automation, Artificial intelligence, Robotics, Big data, Internet of Things (IoT), Machine learning, Upskilling, Reskilling, Deskilling, Skills gap, Job displacement, Workforce adaptation, Technological advancements. 38 articles were successful for the final screening. All selected articles specifically addressed the topic of human resource management demand in the Fourth Industrial Revolution Era, emphasizing the implications of upskilling, reskilling, and deskilling, which provided valuable insights and findings directly related to the study's objective.

Additionally, the articles used were recently published in reputable and peer-reviewed journals to enhance the trustworthiness and reliability of the information presented in the papers. Data were extracted from the articles that met the inclusion criteria to identify seven (7) sub-themes: Industry 4.0, upskilling, reskilling, deskilling, human resource development, workforce transformation, technology impact and organizational change. These sub-themes were synthesized to address the study objectives.

Discussion of Findings

The Implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on Deskilling of Human Resources Management

Deskilling refers to the process by which tasks or jobs that once required a high skill level are simplified and standardized, often through technology or automation, reducing the skill level needed to perform those tasks or jobs. While the 4IR promises to create new job opportunities and enhance productivity, it

also has implications for the skill requirements of the workforce. One of the potential implications of the 4IR is the deskilling of human resources. This happens when machines take over routine and repetitive tasks that human workers previously performed, making their skills and experience obsolete. This is affirmed by (Kunst, 2020; Previtali & Fagiani, 2015; Sambasivan & Veeraraghavan, 2022). The 4IR can accelerate the deskilling process by automating a wide range of tasks that skilled workers previously performed. For example, machine learning algorithms can now analyze data and make predictions more accurately and faster than human analysts, leading to the replacement of some analytical and decision-making tasks.

Similarly, one of the main features of the 4IR is the increased use of automation, which involves using robots and other machines to perform tasks that humans previously did. Robots can now perform physical tasks such as pre-screening, bookkeeping and data entry, onboarding administration, payroll, timekeeping, and benefits administration with greater precision and efficiency than human workers, replacing some manual and technical tasks. This can lead to the deskilling of workers, as they are no longer required to perform specific tasks that machines can do more efficiently and accurately. This is supported by (Loumpourdi, 2021; Sambasivan & Veeraraghavan, 2022; Whitehead et al., 2021), that opined that with the increased use of artificial intelligence, robotics and machine learning, many tasks that humans previously did are being automated. AI-powered chatbots can now handle customer service inquiries, reducing the need for human customer service representatives.

The implications of deskilling on human resources are significant. As tasks are automated, and workers are deskilled, many jobs become redundant leading to job losses. As technology also advances, the skills required for specific jobs will change. Workers who have been deskilled may find it difficult to re-enter the workforce or may need to retrain to acquire new skills. Deskilling can reduce wages as the value of specific skills decreases, significantly impacting workers. The deskilling of workers can also lead to increased inequality, as those who cannot adapt to the changing nature of work may be left behind. The 4IR creates a need for lifelong learning, as workers must continually update their skills to remain relevant. This can be challenging for workers who may not have access to training or education. Human resource professionals need to address the implications of deskilling and develop strategies to support workers in acquiring the skills they need to succeed in the changing world of work (Chigbu & Nekhwevha, 2020; Kunst, 2020).

The Implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on Upskilling of Human Resource Management

Upskilling aims to improve employability, productivity, and competitiveness in the job market. With the introduction of new technologies, the nature of work is changing rapidly, and as a result, new skills and competencies are required. This means that companies need to invest in upskilling their employees to meet the unique demands of the workplace. Some skills that are becoming increasingly important

include digital literacy, data analysis, programming, Cybersecurity, HR software analytics, emotional intelligence and critical thinking (Chakrabarti, 2022; Li, 2022). As automation takes over routine tasks, soft skills such as creativity, problem-solving, and communication become increasingly important. These skills are difficult to automate and are essential for building strong relationships with customers and colleagues. Therefore, human resources professionals must focus on upskilling their employees. This is affirmed by (Taiwo S O & -Magigaba, 2021; Whitehead et al., 2021). The pace of change in the 4IR is unprecedented, so upskilling is no longer a one-time event. Instead, it is a continuous process that requires lifelong learning. Human resources professionals must create a learning culture and provide employees with the resources to keep up with the latest trends and technologies.

Additionally, the 4IR is creating a highly competitive environment and human resources professionals that fail to upskill their employees risk falling behind. Upskilling provides a competitive advantage by enabling companies to be more innovative, efficient, and customer-focused. The 4IR is highly complex, and no single person or department can be an expert in all the emerging technologies. Therefore, collaboration is essential. Human resources professionals must create a culture of cooperation and allow employees to work together and learn from each other. This finding is supported by (Pató et al., 2022; Puhovichova & Jankelova, 2022).

The Implication of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on Reskilling of Human Resources Management

Reskilling is often used to address skills gaps, increase workforce productivity, and enhance employability in a rapidly evolving job market. Human resources management personnel need to reskill to develop a deep understanding of learning and development principles, familiar with the latest technologies, project management skills, communication and analytical skills.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is driven by automation and artificial intelligence, which have the potential to replace human jobs. However, there will still be a need for human intervention to ensure that the technologies are functioning correctly. Therefore, human resources professionals must reskill their employees to operate and maintain the devices effectively. Also, employees who the automation will displace can be reskilled to operate and maintain the machines. Human resources professionals must develop reskilling programs to ensure employees have the necessary skills to operate and maintain the appliances.

Additionally, the Fourth Industrial Revolution has led to the digitization of many processes, which has increased the risk of cyber-attacks. Human resources professionals must reskill their employees to ensure they are aware of cyber-attack risks and are equipped to prevent them. Also, human resources professionals must have a cyber-security plan to ensure their data is secure. The Fourth Industrial Revolution has also led to increased data collection and analytics, and human resources professionals will need to reskill their employees to ensure that they are proficient in data analysis. With

the increasing use of technology, soft skills such as communication, collaboration, and problem-solving have become more critical. Human resources professionals must reskill their employees to ensure they have the necessary soft skills to work effectively with others.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has led to a rapid pace of technological change, which means that employees will need to continue learning throughout their careers to stay relevant. Companies will need to develop reskilling programs to ensure that their employees are equipped with the necessary skills to keep up with the pace of change. The Fourth Industrial Revolution has significant implications for human resources management and necessitates reskilling human resources. The reskilling of human resources will be critical to the success of companies in the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Fourth Industrial Revolution era significantly transformed human resources management practices. One of the most significant changes is the need for the workforce to upskill, reskill and deskilling of human resource responsibility. With the rise of new technologies and automation, there is an increased demand for human resource personnel with advanced programming, data analytics, and artificial intelligence skills. Organizations and human resource management need to create opportunities for upskilling and reskilling the workforce to keep up with the changing job requirements. The Fourth Industrial Revolution has also resulted in the displacement of specific jobs due to automation. HRM must be able to identify the skills that are becoming obsolete and reskill employees to meet the needs of the changing job market. Some tasks humans previously performed are automated, reducing the skill level required for certain jobs. HRM must ensure that employees affected by deskilling are provided with training and opportunities for upskilling to acquire new skills to remain employable.

The finding of this study resonates with the the Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC) theory which suggests that technological advancements and the introduction of new technologies can have differential effects on the demand for different types of skills in the workforce. The SBTC theory argues that technological change tends to favor workers with higher levels of skills while potentially reducing demand for workers with lower levels of skills or specific set of skills. It suggests that organizations need to adapt their HR strategies and invest in developing the skills that are in high demand in the evolving technological landscape.

This review revealed new or emerging skill demands that driven by technological advancements and automation. It also identified specific skills that are increasingly in demand, such as data analysis, artificial intelligence, robotics, and cybersecurity. These insights can inform HRM practices to ensure the workforce possesses the necessary skills.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are presented:

- (1) In the deskilling implication on human resource management, management should consider alternative approaches to job design that prioritize the development of new skills and knowledge and provide continuous learning and development opportunities to ensure employees are equipped with the skills required to adapt to changing job requirements.
- (2) In upskilling implications on human resource management, organizations should invest in training and development programs to upskill employees in new technologies and advanced skills.
- (3) In the reskilling implication of Human resource management, regular skill gap assessments should be conducted by human resource experts to identify the skills that are becoming obsolete and reskill employees accordingly.

Suggestions for Further Research

Human resource management demand in the fourth industrial revolution era and its implication on Upskilling, Reskilling and Deskilling is a novel field that has not been fully explored. Hence there is a need for further research to investigate emerging skill requirements, such as digital literacy, critical thinking, and adaptability, and identify strategies for preparing the workforce to meet these demands.

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